

INFLUENCE AND DEVELOPMENT OF LANGUAGES

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Abstract. This article talks about the interaction of languages and the laws of their development, history.

Key words: languages, era, comparative-historical, word, point of view.

ВЛИЯНИЕ И РАЗВИТИЕ ЯЗЫКОВ

Аннотация. В статье говорится о взаимодействии языков и закономерностях их развития, истории.

Ключевые слова: языки, эпоха, сравнительно-исторический, слово, точка зрения.

It would not be wrong to say that the first steps in the field of linguistics in the world were taken into account from the times when the need for communication between people was felt. The science of linguistics is one of the sciences with the longest history. It began to develop in Ancient India and Ancient Greece (Greece) a few hundred years before our time. The issue of the existence of a connection between a word and its conceptual essence caused a lot of debate among scientists and philosophers of ancient Greece. As a result of these, the analyzes and observations were finally based on the initial theoretical ideas about the vocabulary of the language and the emergence of words. In the first half of the 19th century, great achievements were made in the field of linguistics.

In particular, in this period, the comparative-historical method was formed in linguistics, and in accordance with it, the science of language began to be called the science of comparative-historical linguistics. During this period, realizing that the European languages are closely related to the Sanskrit (ancient Indian) language, the interrelationship and interdependence of these languages began to be seriously studied. German scientists Franz Bopp (1791-1867), Jacob Grimm (1785-1863), Danish scientist Rasmus Rask (1787-1832), MS scientist Alexander Vostokov (1781-1864), Czech scientist Dobrovsky (1753-1829) made great contributions. The interesting thing is that these scientists met at one point in the development of the method, idea and principles of comparative-historical study of the language independently and at the same time. In 1818, F. Bopp's work entitled "On the Inflectional System of the Sanskrit Language Compared to the Greek, Latin, Persian and German Years" was published. In it, Iliopp showed the morphological structure of these languages. In addition, he justified the fact that Indo-European languages have many commonalities, for example, the same grammatical structure, and that these languages originated from the same root.

In the same year, R. Rask's scientific work entitled "Studies on the origin of the Old Norse language or the Icelandic language" was published. R. Rask is also his. In his work, he emphasizes that determining the closeness and similarity of languages is based on their grammatical structure, the harmony of sounds. In 1819, the first volume of Y. Grimm's "German Grammaticals" was published. In 1920, a scientific work entitled "Remarks on the Slavic language" written by A. Vostokov was published. In these announced works, a new method of studying human languages from a historical point of view was introduced.

In general, scientists who made a great contribution to the development of the science of linguistics are Ferdinand de Saussure, Grosse, Baudouin de Courtenay, N.V. Krashevsky, the Indian scholar Panini who lived in the 4th century BC, Greek linguists Democritus, Epicurus, Heraclitus, Uzbek linguists Mahmud Koshg. Ariy, Zamakhshari, Alisher Navoi. They participated in the creation of language science with their significant scientific ideas and research. Linguistics prepares to understand the problems of general linguistics and, at the same time, provides basic information about language.

In the primitive community, people lived as clans. Several clans formed a tribe. These associations had their own language. Tribes begin to multiply and spread. Kindred tribes in a distant region unite into a union of tribes speaking different dialects of the same language.

It is the common language of tribal unions, and some tribal languages take the status of dialects in relation to the tribal language. A union of tribes constitutes a nation. One of the main characteristics of a nation is the presence of a national language. Dialects and national languages have been multiplying since the period of seed production. As the dialects diverge, a new language emerges. A change in quantity leads to a change in quality. As time passes, the distance increases and new languages appear. It is a phenomenon of differentiation and integration. The proliferation of dialects and the emergence of new languages is called differentiation in linguistics, that is, the separation of languages into dialects. A language serves a whole nation, and a dialect is only for a group of people. Language is multi-functional, it is a general means of communication, that is, an invariant tool. The main features of the nation are common territory, common language, and common cultural units. A union that embodies these signs is called a nation. The language of this association is called the national language.

The difference between a national language and a folk language is the presence of a literary form in it. The cultural culture of each nation is reflected in this language. The history of language development is inextricably linked with the history of society. Different relations between different peoples, trade and cultural relations, and wars have an impact on the development of the language.

It affects some languages more and others less. There is no pure language in the world. For example, 30% of English vocabulary is pure English words, and the rest are borrowed from Romance and Eastern languages. In cross-linguistics, one can talk about substrate and superstate (underlayer and superlayer). Both concepts are elements of the defeated language in the winning language. The acquisition of speech from one language to another is not part of the substrate. In the substrate, the winning language displaces the losing language, and the losing language has a significant influence on the winning language. In the superstate, the foreign language has a significant influence on the local language, but it cannot displace it. There will be no revolution in language.

Changes in the language take place gradually in an evolutionary way. There is no stagnation in language development. It is always evolving. During its historical development, any language enriches and develops its vocabulary at the expense of internal and external sources. This general law of language development also applies to Uzbek. In general, no language in the world can develop in absolute isolation from other languages. Therefore, the vocabulary of any language contains elements of other languages that interact with it. On the basis of mutual relations between peoples, the phenomenon of interlingual word exchange or mutual word acquisition occurs.

Because as a result of the mutual relations between peoples, together with the acquired material objects and spiritual and educational concepts, in turn, the lexemes that represent ulam also change. Many linguists of the world have conducted a lot of scientific research on the interaction of languages. In most of the conducted studies, this issue was approached from a socio-historical and psychological point of view, that is, by studying the history of a specific language, the influence of other languages during its development in one or another period of history, and as a result, languages there was an exchange of words between them.

Of course, the quantitative results of cross-linguistic communication vary from language to language. Among the languages of the world, no language can be found anywhere that has not been influenced by other languages or has not given its vocabulary to other languages. Also, no living language can guarantee that it will not interact with another language.

It is a well-known fact that the languages of peoples who interact with each other influence each other, serve to enrich each other, and this interaction is effective in the lexicon. Interactions between peoples and the influence of languages on each other have their own characteristics in different periods and under different conditions. Such interaction is weak in some periods, and significant and effective in another period. At the same time, such an interaction is sometimes spontaneous, while in some periods it needs to be established on the basis of certain laws and regulations, and active human intervention is required. In fact, the ancient Uzbek language interacted with many other languages in different historical periods. Therefore, the vocabulary of the Uzbek literary language contains elements of many languages such as ancient Uyghur, Sogdian, Chinese, Arabic, Mongolian, Persian-Tajik. These languages influenced the composition of the Uzbek vocabulary in different periods, to different degrees, and in different ways. Accordingly, the number of words transferred to the Uzbek language is also different. The same situation can be fully observed in all terminological systems of the Uzbek language.

Below, we tried to present the topic of the languages that influenced the historical development of the Uzbek language and interacted with it, using the terminology of Uzbek literature. It should be noted that, as in some Turkic languages, in the early stages of the formation of Uzbek literary terminology (from the 11th-12th centuries to the beginning of the 20th century), the vocabulary of the Uzbek literary language was the main source for creating terms related to the same issue. It is not used enough. First of all, the Arabic language, and then the Persian-Tajik language had the main advantage in this direction. Therefore, Arabic and Persian-Tajik languages played a significant role in the formation of Uzbek literary terminology.

REFERENCES

1. Nurmonov A., Rasulov R. O'zbek tili jadvallarda. —T.: O'qituvchi, 1993.
2. Реформатский А.А. Введение в языковедение. — М.: Аспект пресс, 2003.
3. Sodiqov A, Abduazizov A, Irisqulov M. Tilshunoslikka kirish. -T., 1981.
4. Shermatov A, Choriyev B. Umumiy tilshunoslik kursidan mustaqil ishlar. — T.: O'qituvchi, 1989.
5. Qo 'chqortoyev /., Qo 'chqortoyeva R. Tilshunoslikka kirish. - T., 1975.
6. Hojiyev A. Tilshunoslik terminlarining izohli lug'ati. — T.: O'zbekiston Milliy ensiklopediyasi, 2002.

7. Turumbetova Z., Abdiraxmanova D. INFLUENCE OF THE SOCIAL ENVIRONMENT ON THE BEHAVIOR OF PRESCHOOL CHILDREN //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 5. – С. 1196-1199.
8. УЗБЕКИСТАН С. О. Р. КАРАКАЛПАКСКИЙ ГОСУДАРСТВЕННЫЙ УНИВЕРСИТЕТ КАФЕДРА ПЕДАГОГИКИ И ПСИХОЛОГИИ ЗЮ ТУРУМБЕТОВА. – 2022.
9. Turumbetova Z. Y. INTEGRATIVE APPROACH TO HIGHER EDUCATION AS A PEDAGOGICAL PROBLEM //ИНТЕГРАЦИЯ НАУКИ, ОБЩЕСТВА, ПРОИЗВОДСТВА И ПРОМЫШЛЕННОСТИ: ПРОБЛЕМЫ И ВОЗМОЖНОСТИ. – 2022. – С. 51-55.